

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS OF “OPLAN KALUSUGAN SA DepEd” IN BAYAMBANG DISTRICT 1

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the status of the implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” in District 1 of Bayambang covering the period of SY 2018-2019. Based on the findings, one component of ‘Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd’ program which is the School-Based Feeding Program had not been fully implemented as assessed by three groups of respondents. This indicates that there is a need to improve activities under these areas in order to attain the highest level of implementation. Water, Sanitation and Hygiene on the part of teachers and focal persons under this component still needs improvement, for them this had not been fully implemented. However, school heads considered this WASH as fully implemented and no need for improvement. Teachers, Focal persons and School Administrators encountered less serious problems in carrying out the program activities. Respondents in this study have the same assessment on the level of seriousness of problems they encountered in the implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” program.

Keywords. oplan kalusugan, implementation status, water sanitation hygiene, DepEd

1 Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), a country’s investment for an effective school health program is considered to be a cost-effective investment as it simultaneously improves health and education. Health-promoting practices can significantly reduce many of the current and future causes of death, diseases and disability in the Department of Education (DepEd). These practices include detecting and referring sick and malnourished children to receive healthcare while the children are still in school. Early detection is critical and school administrators, staff, and teachers are in a position to identify the nutrition and hygienic issues.

DepEd launched the “Oplan Kalusugan sa Department of Education” (OK sa DepEd) which is a convergence of DepEd’s health programs, plans, policies, and activities for their effective and efficient implementation at the school level, in partnership with various stakeholders.

Ultimately, “OK sa DepEd” shall redound towards improving school performance or learning indicators of the learners, such as improved attendance and class participation, improved completion and achievement levels, and reduced drop-out.

Health and nutrition are concerns that need the attention of all sectors because they directly impact on our education and economic system. Thus, the Department of Education is intensifying its medical, dental and nursing services throughout the year as a preventive measure to protect the students, teachers and non-teaching personnel against diseases. It also conducts nutritional assessment, including the eating habits of students so that the information gathered can be used to map out a more responsive health and nutrition intervention.

In 1990 the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) established the Joint Monitoring Program for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene (JMP). Since then, the Joint Monitoring Program (JMP) has been instrumental in establishing global norms to benchmark and compare progress in water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) across countries.

The global effort to achieve sanitation and water for all by 2030 is extending beyond the household to include institutional settings, such as schools, healthcare facilities and workplaces. This has been reinforced by global education for all eight (8) strategies highlighting how WASH in schools improves access to education and learning outcomes, particularly for girls, by providing a safe, inclusive and equitable learning environment. This report is the first comprehensive global assessment of WASH in schools and establishes a baseline for the SDG period, (Joint Monitoring Program WASH-in -Schools 2018).

Bayambang Central School, where the researcher is currently teaching, is one of the schools in District I of Bayambang that has also some problems regarding health and nutrition of learners. Based on the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) Form 3 report School Year 2018-2019 there are 256 learners Bayambang Central School, where the researcher is currently teaching, is one of the schools in District I of Bayambang that has also some problems regarding health and nutrition of learners. Based on the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) Form 3 report School Year 2018-2019 there are 256 learners.

2 Review of Related Literature

The literature gathered from Jovana Dodos (2017) and from the statement of former Education Secretary Armin Luistro (Philippine Daily Inquirer March 21, 2016) are relevant to present study since they both agree on the importance of the integration of Water, Sanitation, Hygiene and Nutrition in Schools.

The editorial which featured the impact of school food consumption on children's cognition, educational attainment and social development and cited the significance of school feeding program. The study of Jasper, et. al. (2012), Antwi-Agyie et. al. (2017) and Jordanova et. al. (2015) deals on the effectiveness of Water, Sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) in schools.

Another relevance of Borja (2016) study deals on the Status and Problems in Health and Nutrition Program. Her study also employed the descriptive method of research and the data gathering instrument was a questionnaire.

Otieno (2014), the study focused on the influence of school-feeding program on academic performance. All the studies cited and the present investigation focused on the nutritional assessment in terms of school-based feeding program and water, sanitation and hygiene of the respondents in school. Evaluation of the effectiveness was also done in the former studies in order to improve or enhance the health and well-being of the subjects. In summary, the researcher found all the related studies and literatures to have bearing on the concerns of the present study.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study used the descriptive-survey research design because it is the most direct and economic choice to begin to understand the status of the implementation of "Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd" in Bayambang District 1. Descriptive research is derived from a broad class of non-experimental studies with the purpose of describing characteristics of a phenomenon as it is occurring.

3.2 Respondents

This study used the descriptive-survey research design because it is the most direct and economic choice to begin to understand the status of the implementation of "Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd" in Bayambang District 1. Descriptive research is derived from a broad class of non-experimental studies with the purpose of describing characteristics of a phenomenon as it is occurring.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To obtain valid and accurate results from the data that were gathered, appropriate statistical tools were employed by the researcher.

To determine the Implementation Status of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” in District 1 of Bayambang in terms of nutritional assessment school-based feeding program (SBFP) and water sanitation and hygiene (WASH), the average weighted mean was employed and results were interpreted using a 4-point Likert scale as shown: (Table 1):

Table 1. Scale for determining implementation level of “Oplan Kalusugan sa Deped”

Mean Scale	Description
3.50-4.00	Highly Implemented
2.50-3.49	Moderately Implemented
1.50-2.49	Slightly Implemented
1.00-1.49	Not Implemented

To determine the extent of seriousness of the problems encountered by school administrators, focal persons and teachers in terms of nutritional assessment school-based feeding program (SBFP) and water sanitation and hygiene (WASH), the average weighted mean was used and the assessment was interpreted using the 4-point Likert scale as shown in the following:

Table 2. Scale for determining the seriousness of problems encountered by stakeholders

Mean Scale	Description
3.50-4.00	Very Serious
2.50-3.49	Moderately Serious
1.50-2.49	Less Serious
1.00-1.49	Not Serious

Based on the assessment results, the problems encountered were ranked according to the magnitude of the combined average weighted mean.

To determine the significant difference in the assessment by the focal persons, school administrators and teachers on the implementation of the “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” in terms of School-Based feeding program (SBFP); Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH); and the level of seriousness of the problems encountered the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed

4 Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd”

Table 3 presents the assessment made by the teachers, focal persons, and school administrators in terms of activities carried out under this area.

Table 3. Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” Along School-Based Feeding Program

Indicators	Teachers		Focal Persons		School Administrators		Overall	
	I. School-Based Feeding Program		WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE
	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE
1. Conduct of orientation training for school implementers on the mechanics of the feeding program, including their respective roles and responsibilities.	2.99	MI	3.32	MI	3.50	HI	3.27	MI
2. Conduct assessment of nutritional status for: a. baseline data b. endline data	3.07	MI	3.36	MI	3.64	HI	3.36	MI
3. Conduct medical and dental examination before the start of feeding program.	2.96	MI	3.59	HI	3.23	MI	3.26	MI
4. Conduct deworming to the beneficiaries.	2.98	MI	3.50	HI	3.41	MI	3.30	MI
5. Conduct of feeding utilizing feeding program menu cycle.	3.01	MI	3.55	HI	3.59	HI	3.38	MI
6. Conduct of feeding to the beneficiaries for 120 feeding days.	2.89	MI	3.55	HI	3.45	MI	3.30	MI
7. Discussion on health and nutrition topics during the feeding activity.	2.97	MI	3.59	HI	3.59	HI	3.38	MI
8. Establishment of “Gulayan sa Paaralan Program” and backyard vegetable gardening to augment the feeding program.	2.93	MI	3.50	HI	3.41	MI	3.28	MI
9. Conduct group daily hand washing and tooth brushing activities to impart development of positive health-promoting values and behaviors.	3.01	MI	3.36	MI	3.36	MI	3.24	MI
10. Conduct monitoring of the program.	3.02	MI	3.45	MI	3.36	MI	3.28	MI
Average Weighted Mean	2.98	MI	3.48	MI	3.45	MI	3.30	MI

It can be seen from the table that all activities under SBFP are rated as “Moderately Implemented” by the teachers. However, as assessed by the focal persons most of the activities are rated as “Highly Implemented” except four activities which were rated “Moderately Implemented” such as: conduct of orientation training for school implementers on the mechanics of the feeding program including respective roles and responsibilities (WM=3.32), conduct assessment of nutritional status for baseline and endline data (WM=3.36), conduct group daily hand washing and tooth brushing (WM=3.36) and conduct monitoring of the program (WM=3.45).

4.2 Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” Along Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH)

Table 4 shows the level of implementation and it is evident that teachers rated the activities along water as “Moderately Implemented” with the average weighted mean of 3.01. However, the protection of water against all types of contamination, regular cleaning and maintenance as well as repair of water supply facilities are rated as Highly Implemented.

Table 4. Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” Along Water

Indicators II. Water, Sanitation, hygiene (WASH)	Teachers		Focal Persons		School Administrators		Overall	
	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE
A. Water								
1. Regular supply of safe drinking water in school.	3.00	MI	3.45	MI	3.64	HI	3.36	MI
2. Regular monitoring of water quality in accordance with the latest National Standards for drinking water, to protect the water supply from all types of contamination within the school premises.	2.98	MI	3.55	HI	3.64	HI	3.39	MI
3. Organized system to make adequate clean water for hand washing, toilet use, menstrual hygiene management, and cleaning purposes available to all students during school hours.	2.98	MI	3.50	HI	3.32	MI	3.27	MI
4. Installed rainwater catchment system to insure water supply for proper hygiene and sanitation during emergencies.	3.00	MI	3.36	MI	3.45	MI	3.27	MI
5. Regular cleaning and maintenance activities as well as repair of water supply facilities.	3.07	MI	3.59	HI	3.59	HI	3.42	MI
AWM	3.01	MI	3.49	MI	3.53	HI	3.34	MI

Table 5. Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” Along Sanitation

Indicators II. Water, Sanitation, hygiene (WASH)	Teachers		Focal Persons		School Administrators		Overall	
	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE
Sanitation								
1. Access to functional toilets with individual hand washing for boys and girls in school.	3.00	MI	3.32	MI	3.64	HI	3.32	MI
2. Adequate and proper septage and waste water disposal.	2.99	MI	3.59	HI	3.64	HI	3.41	MI
3. Proper segregation and disposal of biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste materials.	3.05	MI	3.55	HI	3.45	MI	3.35	MI
4. Follow the prohibition on the burning of garbage.	3.02	MI	3.36	MI	3.36	MI	3.25	MI
5. School personnel in charge of food handling and preparations are properly trained and certified based on the standards of the Code of Sanitation.	2.96	MI	3.41	MI	3.59	HI	3.32	MI
AWM	3.00	MI	3.45	MI	3.54	HI	3.33	MI

Along sanitation services, teachers rated all activities as “Moderately Implemented” with average weighted mean of 3.00. On the other hand, out of five activities to be carried out only two are rated as “Highly Implemented” by the focal persons namely: adequate and proper septage and waste water disposal (WM=3.59), proper segregation and disposal of biodegradable and nonbiodegradable waste materials (WM=3.55). Noticeably, however, the activity that follow the prohibition on the burning of garbage with weighted mean of 3.36 and proper segregation and disposal of biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste materials (WM= 3.45) are “Moderately Implemented” as assessed by the school administrators.

Table 6. Level of Implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” Along Hygiene

Indicators	Teachers		Focal Persons		School Administrators		Overall	
	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE	WM	DE
II. Water, Sanitation, hygiene (WASH)								
C. Hygiene								
1. Adequate supply of toothpaste, toothbrushes, and soap available to all students.	3.09	MI	3.41	MI	3.50	HI	3.33	MI
2. Availability of sanitary pads in school facilities such as school canteen, clinic or guidance counselor’s office as well as covered garbage bins for proper disposal.	3.04	MI	3.64	HI	3.45	MI	3.38	MI
3. Information advocacy materials on reproductive health and hygiene education for boys and girls that integrate essential menstruation-related components shall be provided to teachers.	3.01	MI	3.32	MI	3.59	HI	3.31	MI
4. Privacy and securities facilities used for menstrual hygiene management.	3.01	MI	3.50	HI	3.55	HI	3.35	MI
AWM	3.04	MI	3.47	MI	3.52	HI	3.34	MI

Table 6 shows that all activities under hygiene as assessed by the teachers are “Moderately Implemented” (AWM=3.04). However, it can be seen from the same table under hygiene services that there are four activities to be carried out. The focal persons assessed the specific activities as “Moderately Implemented”.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

One component of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” program which is the School-Based Feeding Program had not been fully implemented as assessed by the three groups of respondents. This indicates that there is a need to improve activities under these areas in order to attain the highest level of implementation. Water, Sanitation and Hygiene on the part of teachers and focal persons under this component still needs improvement. For them this had not been fully implemented. However, school heads considered this WASH as fully implemented and no need for improvement.

There is a significant difference in the assessment of school administrators, focal persons and teachers as regards the implementation status of the School Based Feeding Program as well as Water, Sanitation and Hygiene Services. Researchers, Focal persons and School Administrators encountered less serious problems in carrying out the program activities. Respondents in this study have the same assessment on the level of seriousness of problems they encountered in the implementation of “Oplan Kalusugan sa DepEd” program.

In order to attain the highest level of implementation in terms of School-Based Feeding Program, organize regular information exchange sessions, and strengthen the link of stakeholders like private sectors to enjoin the program. Factsheets or information materials should be explained well, but most important suggestion is that timeframe given must be reasonable so that preparing the data is realistic also known as time tracking of results.

Integrated plans must be supported by sufficient financing, effective coordination and stronger channeling especially in disseminating information without delays. Teachers, focal persons and school administrators should be committed in implementing the program. They should strive to fully implement their “OK sa DepEd” program particularly in SBFP and WASH.

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